

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Okay. Hello. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this research. My name is Anna Makarudze. I'm pursuing a master's in Software Engineering, integrating an Institute of Technology in Sweden. My study is focused on understanding perspectives of developers with regards to on software dependence management offers us to build management, especially with the rise of supply chain attacks.

And I'm focusing on 5 web frameworks, Django. Next to Js spring book, Laravel, and Rubon rail. Participation in this research is entirely for them that you can withdraw from the interview at any time. will not retain any personal data or identifiable information.

Your name, your e-mail address or any identifiable details not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions that you're not comfortable answering and your responses will remain anonymous.

Then the interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the organization reported that.

Speaker 2

I see. Good.

Speaker 1

And then before we start, would you kindly introduce yourself and the project? Yeah, the developer or contributor or maintainer, and also the web framework, which you are mainly first in of the fact that I mentioned.

Speaker 2

Of course. So I'm here as a backend developer. I've been working as a Python main backend web developer for last 10, 12 years, and currently I'm active in open source community with Python. I've been active in Django community for the last couple years. As you can imagine, my framework of choice is Django, and I'm interested in the security

issues around open source projects. I'm trying to support several different organizations, some local, some global. but I kind of think that people are not really serious enough about the security issues and the open source contribution processes. So I'm just trying to push those conversations in different communities for a while, but I saw that they don't really work out and I'm curious about what's going on in the community, how can I contribute, and here I am.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And you said you're in the Django community, and I just wanted you to explain what is it that you do towards the Django content in terms of code. Do you contribute code? Are you a test or triage issues, review pull requests?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I'm mostly active with the projects around Django, not Django core itself.

And physically, I'm unfortunately, far away from the Django organizations, physical organizations, so I help with organizing local events as far as I can, and also I'm an active maintainer in Django Commons organizations, so the tools, the third parties around Django, like I'm trying to... apply their basic maintenance tasks.

I don't fix every bug that I think is interesting, but I try to help people to automate their developer workflows, CI/CD pipelines, and apply the best modern tooling to those workflows and try to streamline a Python workflow, a development workflow for those projects.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. Okay, so you mentioned maintaining some third party Django apps. Are they open source or are they like?

Speaker 2

They are all open source. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Would you mind naming a few of those?

Speaker 2

Yeah, for a while a couple of years ago, I was one of the maintainers of Django Graphene and Strawberry came out and we switched to different tools. Nowadays, I guess I'm one of the maintainers of Django Waffle.

Like, I'm contributing around 50 different packages, so I'm not really sure which permissions I have, which one of them. But yeah, anything in Django Comms organization, you can just find my comments with updates, with cleaning, with security stuff in them. I guess there are 12 packages that are including Django debug toolbar and some of the most used packages with Django. Outside of the organization, Django Commons, I was a member of Jazz Band. They are like disbanding now, but again, there are too many packages that like I could give you my GitHub profile and you can see them there, but I'm not sure it fits the anonymization kind of the things. Okay, yeah, I've I've heard of Django Commons, and I joined JazzBand, which has been a while, but I didn't slightly do much on it.

Speaker 1

So alright. And okay, so my next question would be, how are security issues handled within your projects like if they are reports for the tools that you have maintained in jungle common?

Speaker 2

To be honest, I'm not even really sure. Like if we are talking about code-based security issues, I know that like the main policy with Django is there is a security line, you submit your findings there, there's an expectation of formatting, like you don't say this is insecure and fix it, but explain what you find. With Django Commons, My limited knowledge says that like it depends on the contributor and maintainer because like Django Commons administration doesn't try to handle everything in those projects.

That's more like a vertical hierarchy kind of thing. Like if you are maintaining one project, the overall expectation is that you maintain that project, not the admins. Admins are there to enable you or help you with your contribution process or maintaining process. But the organization itself, as far as I know, doesn't really concern about the individual security

But let's say if there is a big security issue with the platform itself, like maybe one of the automation scripts related to administration of the organization, that's the admin's job to fix or let's say GitHub has some weird security issue that affects all of the projects.

Again, that's admin level thing, but other than that, like if Django Debug Toolbar has a security issue, as far as I know, it's the responsibility of the individual packages maintainers, not the organization.

So my best guess here from my limited knowledge is it depends on the project and the

Speaker 1

And how different is that from, you said you're also part of Jazz Band, how would you, how different is that from Jaspin's processing?

Speaker 2

Yeah, Jazz Band's process is, I mean, I would like to be nice about it, but it's kind of horrible to be honest because like I found some serious issues a couple years ago with Jazz Band and there wasn't even a single person that I can report those organizational workflow level issues that affects all of the packages in the Jazz Band organization and nowadays the organization is getting disbanded. I'm happy for it, but because it was a ticking time bomb and I'm still expecting a huge supply chain attack from Jazz Band organization because as someone with a average literacy on how to use GitHub, you can just join the Jazz Band organization without any approval. You can just join any project without any approval. And from my personal testing, what I saw from projects, there are almost no merge protection for any of the projects. So anyone on the internet can just join the organization, can just join the maintainers group of a project, and you can merge whatever you want. And if there's a release script, you can release whatever you want. So Jazz Band doesn't do

Speaker 1

Oh, okay. Thank you. I wasn't aware of. All right.

Speaker 2

Yeah, that's fantastic. Yeah, I know.

Speaker 1

And okay, so with Django Commons, then you need permission to be a maintainer.

Speaker 2

Yeah, like there's a not really official, but there is a approval process. You need to introduce yourself and you need to kind of explain your relation with the, like, you can, let me rephrase that. You can request your approval of joining the Django Commons organization, but if you say I want to contribute X, Y, and Z packages, it's like, It's like how any other package work, like maintainer should know and approve you like personally. So it's not like I want to join this and some organization admin just approves you and you're in like it's personal relations and personal trust and everything.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. My next question would be, how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your project?

Speaker 2

Oh, I mean, I'm trying my best with, um, and the best mean that's the best being is like I do have Renovate in place. So it auto updates my dependencies. I don't prefer GitHub's Dependabot because like I was a contributor in dependable for maybe five or six years and they are not doing well with Python and GitHub's AI push. also created some issues with their security scanning processes. So they are giving some sort of, I don't know, people call it false negative or false positive, but I found in the code QL that like it says there's like, let's say you're using the latest version of Django and because the model's knowledge cutoff is like a year before now and it says this Django version doesn't exist, you should upgrade it not downgrade it. I'm just annotating what they say you should upgrade it. And then it recommends you to downgrade the package to an insecure version.

So anyone following GitHub's security recommendations, code quell, dependable is kind of messing up their whole process. So leaving GitHub's tooling for anything security related was a huge relief and Renovate is helping them other from that. I have Ruff in place with bonded setups. So if there's something in the code itself, it helps. Like I guess I also this more helps a lot like with the overall workflows and supply chain security stuff. And I yeah, that's pretty much all like with all of them in place.

I kind of have a trust in the process because I do know that I don't use unsecured packages. And I do know that like my old workflow actions are pinned to the hash, the images are pinned to the hash and the tools automate them. So it's not something like I can ignore, I can miss or some, I don't know, well intended but not knowledgeable contributor makes a mistake in the repository and create a risk.

So three main tools in the place and I kind of believe they maybe one problem that I couldn't solve it yet, like I guess you heard about the Lite LLM thing last week. They kind of injected a security tool, then that security tool injected a Lite LLM library and PyPi had another injected code attack. So it was a huge thing, but from what I read, like the longest security issue to solve with Python package index take four days and it's the only one generally takes three or four hours to resolve for Python commit to subline check your attacks.

So if I'm waiting, like I forgot the keyword there, but there was a configuration key saying you should wait seven days before merging a new package because that's the overall maturity. So I believe, like, yeah, that's on my to-do list. So I maybe handle that for the projects I'm maintaining. But other than that, I kind of trust in the process and tooling. I'm not sure if it was able to answer your question.

Speaker 1

Yes. My next question would have been, how are you supplying chain attacks and their effects on their projects?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I mean, for example, with Jazz Band case, I kind of do nothing apart from watching the security warnings because that organization is kind of vital for the Python ecosystem and there are so many packages, especially for the Django community, and they are all at risk. I've been aware of this for two years and there is no organization maintainer active and that's also why the organization is being disbanded. So my first, my best attempt is to help projects moving Jazz Band from Django Commons or their, I don't know, related organizations or personal accounts.

But other than that, personally, I don't remember any of the projects I worked on so far being attacked in some kind or being injected. And I don't know, I guess that's also thanks to the tooling, but a couple days from now, we could see that Django, whole Django workflows are failing because they are not pinning their dependencies, they are not pinning their workflow actions, Docker images or anything else like that, and they're kind of slow to handle, I mean, years slow, not hours or days to update their CICD processes.

So couple days from now, if I saw, if I see a Django supply chain security attack, I don't really have any idea to how to handle it. That will be disastrous.

Speaker 1

And what is the decision to update the newer versions of dependence within your project?

Speaker 2

For projects I maintain like whenever they release, like that's also one of the things I need to change because there needs to be a maturity time. But like I don't do maybe every three years, every three months, sorry, update all the things or like I don't have a person saying don't change anything if they don't break. I update regularly. I try to follow. I use the command `uvp list outdated`, and I always prefer to see it clean. And Renovate updates are clean. So whenever the scheduled update time, I just apply them. I don't wait to ignore or push them back.

Speaker 1

And how do you check the maintenance of dependencies in your projects? Like it's common for creators of open source projects to abandon their projects and then they become unmaintained. So how do you check to see each of the projects you are using, each of the dependents you're using in the projects are still being maintained.

Speaker 2

There are a couple things like the tooling in the ecosystem is not the best for that. For example, Django releases a new major version. For example, the 6.0 released a couple months ago and I'm trying to understand which projects are updating themselves. Like I do have an, for example, like I do have an existing project with the...

previous version of Django and I want to update Django and I want to see which projects, which packages support the newest version of Django and there is almost nothing in the ecosystem it helps with that.

Maybe you know something I don't know. I would really like if you could send me anything that cut out. But at some point I created some personal tooling using AI tools to create a front end that you just copy your requirements file or pyproject toml file and it analyzes Python package index API and packages and says this package is updated at this time and it supports this version or that version.

But apart from that, like the ecosystem almost, there is nothing helping with that.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle vulnerable dependencies within your projects? Do you always update them on?

Speaker 2

I mean, updating them is the best way, I guess, but also there is a preemptive way that, like, if I'm looking for a job and the project is using some outdated end-of-life version of Python, I know that the risk factor is too high and I won't be able to update things going around, and there will be some sort of security issues that it will burn people like...extra times and day or weekends and whatever, like I don't prefer to work on that project.

There's also the response of not taking the responsibility aspect of the thing, but from that, like if a project is fairly maintained, I mean open source or property, like I just install renovates and I do have my own configuration, so it's not so noisy because otherwise it creates fatigue.

I don't like that that, but there's some basic grouping configuration in my GitHub. I use that and from that point I just check whatever PR is opened by the tool. Like I also compare like if it's saying that a Docker image is updated and the hash is changed, I compare that hash with the Docker registry so they are matching. But other than that, yeah, I just update and merge every update PR.

Speaker 1

And usually, how long does it take to update vulnerable within your project?

Speaker 2

I mean, if it's not a security issue, I kind of try to update them every week, like on Monday. As today before our meeting, I was checking my GitHub for project updates and I saw that Gunicorn released something, Yuri released something.

I was checking their change log. I try to do them every week if I'm working on a project actively. If I'm not, like, I guess, I don't remember the exact configuration, but for my open source template projects, they are checked automatically every month, except security issues. If there's a security issue, that's an immediate warning and I check it on the same day generally. Yeah, like security issues immediately, other stuff weekly or monthly, depending on the project.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle dependencies that are no longer being maintained if they were already like in your dependency screen?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I mean, that's a good question. I don't have a broad answer for that. Some projects, you can't just get rid of them, but I try to minimize the attack vector, let's say, like I was using something to visualize Django migrations and I know the maintainer, I communicated with them personally and they just don't want to spend any time on that project anymore, but they also believe that the project is so good that they won't, it won't need any updates or feature changes or anything.

So there is a problem with, like I don't want to say some maintainers are, it's wrong for this, but they just like everyone doesn't care about the same things at the same level. So if it's that, like, that package doesn't really accept any requests from the outside world or doesn't use any user input data, it's kind of okay because it works on the code I created. If I'm careful about the code I created, the package, even if it's get injected or created some sort of security issue in it because of not being properly maintained.

It will be contained. I can fork it anytime I want. So I'm not really horrified about it. But for example, the Jazz Band thing, I tried to find any alternative that is not maintained by Jazz Band and it's not always possible. So I mean, I kind of hope that it never happens, but with all security things, it someday happens.

So I'm not doing my best there, I believe, but also the ecosystem is sometimes not helping. So as a open source maintainer, the time I have is limited. So that's done. I mean, not my broadest take on the topic. But yeah.

Speaker 1

Do you use dependence from outside python in Django ecosystems? Maybe Javascript. Ruby. Right? It is simple.

00:23:18 Speaker 2

Yeah, not really much. I mean, I'm focusing on the, like, I work with communities that doesn't really even have the proper understanding of requirements. For example, like, let's say you are creating a Photoshop file and you use some sort of plugin, the Photoshop ecosystem, have developers, but they don't have the proper understanding of requirements and security or supply chain or touch designer committee.

Like I have been working with touch designer for three years. It's a creative tool. And it uses Python. It has an embedded Python and outdated and unsecure Python. It has network libraries to accept some sort of C version of request or HTTPX libraries, like they create a server for that so you can send and receive them from the network. It's a C library and it's not like they were using like five years old version or something. Like there are no concept of updates, requirement updates, the dependency updates.

So first thing I tried to handle that is documenting what they are using because without proper documentation people can't understand what's going on. I tried to contribute to their wiki and they just didn't accept it saying our wiki is not open for contribution, we can't handle that, we don't have the manpower.

And it stayed there. I'm still waiting for like some concert scene to blow up because it got attacked from one of the concert goers because it's really possible. Like there are lasers, there are pyrotechnics, there are sound equipments, millions of things in with a value of million dollars maybe.

And they are working on unsecure networks with unsecure software. So it won't really surprising to me that if some construct will get attacked by a malware and blow up, like it's a horrible thing, but it's the ecosystem.

Speaker 1

Then I for dependencies within your ecosystem taking over abandoned projects. A good consideration. You're already doing that through Django Commons, and you were doing that through Django JSPN. How difficult is it to when the dependence is outside your

ecosystem? For example, they see you were talking about how difficult is it to maintain of independence outside of the ecosystem, though you rely on it. Do we have frozen or something?

Speaker 2

Oops, sorry, I lost the connection for a second.

Speaker 1

Yeah, I know. So I was saying for independence within your ecosystem, taking over abandoned projects is there. Which year the dependency is really common. How difficult is this when the dependency is outside of the ecosystem?

Speaker 2

I mean, it's always hard. Like, I found some patterns that all projects can kind of use. Like, there are some standardized tools like PyUpgrade, DjangoUpgrade, Precommit, Prec, Runaway, it's both, Dependabot depends on whatever you use and Zizmore and Bandit, like I tried to apply all of these for all projects, but some projects doesn't really like them for reasons that I don't appreciate, like I understand, but I appreciate, like for example, Django, if you try to recommend something, some improvement with their workflows, their infrastructure, their CI/CD, they just don't listen.

It's not even a report this to a security. It's like, we know the best. You are someone from outside. We don't want to listen to you. And that's all. And like, it's really, I believe, it's not even... in compliance with their code of conduct.

So Django just doesn't accept any improved proposal from the outside world and there's only four person in the operations team and that's so like whatever they say, it's the love, it's the word of God and still their workflows are taking hours. Like distributed to multiple ecosystems, multiple platforms and people are spending so much time to understand that and they can't properly debug when websites is going down because security updates are not applied, or some other sort of thing.

But like to sum up the my answer, it depends on the maintainers, the previous maintainers or existing maintainers.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And if any of the projects you've worked on ever been exposed to supply chain attack?

Speaker 2

I mean, I don't think so, and it sounds weird thinking how common it is, but I guess the biggest vulnerability that's causing people or projects to be affected from subline checkers and checkers attacks is like, we are using a single outdated Python version and it works and not just updated and when it gets exposed, you can't update your code base immediately because you are using too many updated stuff and updating one of them breaks everything else.

I don't do that. I try to stay preemptive and use, if possible, the latest version of everything. So if something goes bad, I can just update them. But other than that, like, PyPy didn't have any big attacks, or GitHub itself didn't have any big attacks so far, or Jazz Band, even in its current condition, it didn't experience a big supply chain, same security attacks.

So I mean, it can happen any day, but it didn't happen in the past for me. So that's that.

Speaker 1

And what factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Speaker 2

Can you please repeat?

Speaker 1

I'm saying what factors or circumstances help you to address vulnerable dependency within your project? For example, maybe you could want to update your vulnerable dependence, but maybe there's no update or maybe there are some breaking changes. So I want to understand what's an ideal situation for you to be able to update dependencies within your project.

Speaker 2

Okay, so like I'm repeating myself, sorry for that, but like I'm when you try to focus on keeping everything updated, the breaking changes doesn't really happen. Like if I'm already using the latest minor version of a project, a bug fix, a security fix generally means a patch update or bug fix, whatever you call it in somewhere then it's not breaking, it just fixes one single thing, one security issue. So that's the preemptive side of things. Apart from that, there are some issues with the CVEs and the reporting. I had one issue last week.

I saw a security issue in GitHub, a project I hosted in GitHub, and it was saying that Pigments had some sort of issue. I don't remember now, but GitHub is Marking is a security issue because there's a CVE report for that bug.

I checked the repository and maintainers were explaining that it's not really a security issue. It's a bug and their CVE process was too, I don't know the word, but it wasn't really valid, but they couldn't ignore it or reject it because there are no proper mechanisms to push back a CVE or something.

But I checked there the security score or something like the 10 being the worst, 0 being the securest one. It was only 1.2, so I was like, I wasn't worried about that 1.2 security issue score. And it got fixed today. So even when I can't do anything, I just try to understand the surface.

Or like sometimes I see issues with several libraries and the maintainers is not around or someone tried to do something, but I don't know, maybe they used AI and changed too many things at once.

Like I create a PR, I ping developers, I ping maintainers. So there's the organisational side of things. Sometimes I can push or in some projects they fix the issue, they merge the main, but somehow they forget to push a release. So I ping that the maintainers or whoever is responsible or have rights. There is also that, like, if bot doesn't happen, I can't approach the maintainers, I can't communicate with them, I can't fix the issue myself.

And it's really dangerous. Like, there is almost always an alternative. So the worst case is you migrate to another dependency and you just pay the cost. Like, that's the worst case.

Speaker 1

And are there any challenges you face which hinder you from addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

So can you repeat? I'm sometimes losing sound.0

Speaker 1

I'm saying, are there any challenges that might stop you from addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, kind of. I mean, I'm not sure if challenge is the right word, but at the beginning of my understanding with security things better. Like I tried a tool, an organization called OpenSSF, and they do really nice things for open source projects, but they also, like their rules, their recommendations, doesn't always apply all projects.

Like there was a rule saying that any pull request or merge request should be approved at least one other developer maintainer except the author of the PR itself.

So I'm working alone. Most open source maintainers work alone. So there's no one else to approve your PR or give you some sort of security pass that openSSF requires. So understanding where openSSF applies, which sort of rules, applies to which projects. And by the way, it's not like if you ignore that rule and don't apply it, you lose a point there. So it affects your reporting and everything.

But it's kind of like at the beginning, okay, this is have some, I need to use that, I need to understand that. And then like I saw that there are other tools that are this is more Renovate both and they can also have almost like maybe more than half of the things openSSF checks.

So I'm using them now, not openSSF, but the biggest challenge for me to understand which tool fix what, are they fit, or are they asking for something unrealistic, or what is the overall expectation?

And I kind of think many developers are struggling with that. Like I was using, I was talking with someone, I don't want to say the project's name because they are really a big unknown organization, but it's something like almost any Python developer uses and they were saying that we don't like to hash pinning or commit pinning in our dependencies on our workflows because they don't really work, blah, blah, blah, blah.

They don't really work because like GitHub doesn't have the proper log mechanisms for a workflow. Like UV and PyProject Standard has some sort of log file approach to the things and they log everything in place. But with GitHub Actions, you just log your main dependency and if that main dependency has some sort of transitive dependencies that are not locked, your commits or hash pinning doesn't really do almost anything because transitive dependencies can also change, text can change.

So GitHub as a platform has issues. But again, like if you are using GitHub and you are not using hash pinning, Like you are calling for trouble in my opinion. Like you can change a platform, you can try to implement your own solution, but people just like everyone is always busy and in this world everyone is always tired.

So when I say people like this is really important why you are not applying this recommendation is like other companies that not applied this recommendation had these issues, these issues and people like, okay, but I don't think it will happen to us.

And that's all like, that's horrible, I guess, and the literacy there is really low.

Speaker 1

And what recommendations do you have for open source dependence management to mitigate supply chain attack?

Speaker 2

I mean, for our watchers in front of their televisions. GitHub is a really problematic problem in platform in these things because like, again, I was contributing to the Dependabot for five years, six years, even before GitHub bought the project. It was something different, independent and more beautiful in my opinion. They kind of killed it and they have this facets the teacher of a security, like they say they have the tools in place, but they don't really have a proper working tooling. So if you are using GitHub, you may want to think about it again.

But other than that, I'm not really sure, like it depends on the project, depends on the organization. Again, like what I do is having proper tooling, trying to stay updated with the ecosystem and what's going on. But like I still didn't move my projects out from GitHub to anything else because the communities die. Maybe someday whole Django community will move away somewhere and I will move too. But it's a risk that I need to live together for now.

Speaker 1

Thank you. I think that's all from me. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this in that course.

Speaker 2

You're welcome. I hope it was helpful.

Speaker 1

Yes, it was. Thank you. I'll stop recording now. Okay.